

Potential of ecotourism in Arakan-Wawontulap coastal region, North Sulawesi, Indonesia

Oktavianus Lintong, Markus Lasut and Siegfried Berhimpon*

Faculty of Fisheries and Marine Sciences, Sam Ratulangi University, Jalan Kampus Bahu Manado, Indonesia.

ABSTRACT

Arakan-Wawontulap Coastal Region is assumed as a one of coastal region that have potency to be developed as an ecotourism region, especially associated with the conservation of Bunaken National Park. This study aims to evaluate Arakan-Wawontulap Coastal Region potency, and finding strategies to develop this region as a new ecotourism region. Therefore, have been done inventory ecotourism potency, determining the feasibility level of development regions and designing strategies for developing the Arakan-Wawontulap Coastal Region as an ecotourism region. Evaluation the potential of ecotourism conducted on six aspects: Natural Resources, Local Culture, Socio-Economic Local Communities, Infrastructure, Institutional, and Probable Impact. Data were collected using a Questionnaire, Interview, Observation and Documentation method. Data were analyzed according to the research objectives. Descriptive Analysis Method to inventory the potential of ecotourism. Scoring Method (Priskin, 2001; Anonymous, 2009) used to determine the feasibility level of development. SWOT Analysis Method (Rangkuti, 2008) to find the design of development strategies. The result show that natural resource is very affluent. Socio-economic of local communities and institutional condition are adequate, and probable impact is very supportive. The potential for local culture and infrastructure is still low. Therefore, the design of development strategies that can be recommended for this region consists of the strategy of preparatory the region and stakeholders, capacity-building strategy, and marketing strategy. It can be concluded that the Arakan-Wawontulap Coastal Region feasible to be developed as ecotourism region, although by applying some strategy development. In this regard, it is advisable to conduct research on the ecological carrying capacity of a number of objects and attractions that exist in the region, and determine the spatial concept of ecotourism is most appropriate.

Key words: Arakan-Wawontulap Coast, Ecotourism

Introduction

Tourism is one of the leading sector which is driven development in Indonesia, including in North Sulawesi Province. It is quite understandable, since this sector contributed at least 30% of total state rev-

enues (Anonymous, 2008). In North Sulawesi province, tourism became one of the leading sectors of development established by the government (Anonymous, 2005). One strategy pursued by the government to develop the tourism sector is to find, build, and develop a new objects and attractions (obyek and

daya tarik wisata=ODTW). Every place, location, color, or area that has potential, and will be developed into ODTW, so expect more and more tourists will visit the area.

In North Sulawesi province is believed there are a few places, locations, hue, and the region that have potential for tourism but has not been developed, including in coastal areas. One is Arakan-Wawontulap Coastal Region. Arakan-Wawontulap is one of a conservation area which is a part of the Bunaken National Park (BNP). This coastal region is usually called Southern BNP. In this region there are ten villages, namely Poopoh, Teling, Kumu, Pinasungkulan, Rap-rap, Arakan, Sondaken, Pungkol, Wawontulap, and Popareng. This coastal region is located in the western peninsula of North Sulawesi, and administratively included in the South Minahasa district and Minahasa district (Figure 1).

The development trend of world tourism industry increasingly highlight the spirit of ecotourism. In this case, the Arakan-Wawontulap Coastal Region believed to be reasonable developed into a new ecotourism region. Coastal resources that exist in this area, both aquatic and terrestrial resources, has a value that can be utilized. When connected with park

management strategies, the development of this area is urgently needed. A greater pressure on the Northern BNP, especially in Bunaken Island, by the presence of tourist activity, requires an ongoing deployment spots the object of the visiting. Coastal resources in the southern region, believed to be no less important and valuable when compared to the northern park. Even the coastal area of Arakan-Wawontulap have distinct characteristics, so that the utilization patterns tend to vary with the pattern that can be applied in other parts of the BNP (Mehta, 1999; Turak & DeVantier, 2003; Anonymous, 2009).

In connection with the use of coastal areas as ecotourism, there are at least six (6) aspects that need to be studied. These aspects are of natural resources, local culture, socio-economy of local communities, infrastructure, institutional, and possible impacts (Priskin, 2001; Darsoprajitno, 2002; Damanik and Weber, 2006; Fauzi, 2006; Dahuri *et al.*, 2008). The six aspects are also evaluated its presence in the region want to the Arakan-Wawontulap coast. So far, still very limited information that can illustrate these aspects, but the information is very important in order to determine the feasibility and development strategy of the Arakan coast-Wawontulap as

Fig. 1 Arakan-Wawontulap Coastal Region, North Sulawesi Province, Indonesia

Table 1. Ecosystems Attractive in Waters

No.	Ecosystem	Name of Situs	Location	Attractive Value
1.	Coast	1) Tanjung Kelapa	Poopoh Village	Sloping black sand beach (BTNB, 2010). The waters in front of those, is one of the dive spot with characteristic sloping, sandy, mini exotic biota can be found as can be found in the waters of Lembah Strait.
		2) Blok 8	Kumu Village	White sandy beach, at low tide reef mounds visible on the left and right.
		3) Patuku	Pinasungkulan Village	Sloping white sandy beach and calm, surrounded by mangroves, crabs are often found.
		4) Tambelang	Popareng Village	White sandy beach with waves that are very quiet.
2.	Mangrove	1) Kalaween	Pungkol Village	The area of dense mangrove and strictly maintained its existence by the village community.
		2) Sondaken	Sondaken Village	The area of dense mangrove. Although located close to the settlement residents, but conditions are still awake.
		3) Wawontulap	Wawontulap Village	Areas of dense mangroves along the coast until the waters Popareng village.
3.	Coral reef	Four (4) diving spots: Poopoh (TI TOI III), Betlehem, Tanjung Kelapa, Tatapaan (Kai, 2009).		Can be accessed throughout the year regardless of season, still very natural, not much visited, with a characteristic slope, slope into the wall and the lagoon, a sloping reef flat and wide, supported by seagrass beds and mangrove ecosystems are still quite wide and awake, very well good for snorkeling

Table 2. Attractive Biota for Ecotourism

No.	Name of Biota	Observation Location	Attractive Value
1.	Dugong (Dugong dugong)	Popareng Kumu Pinasungkulan (in front of Batu Lubang) Wawontulap Pungkol Arakan	Dugong looks very cute and adorable, very close to the beach, as has been benign. Often seen in groups, foraging in a vast expanse of seagrass or on the fringe of the mangrove area. On the beach of Kumu was last seen four individuals Dugong on March 10, 2010 At 1 pm, located on a bed of seagrass for approximately 2 hours.
2.	Dolphin	Tatapaan Poopoh	Gangs of dolphins are often seen swimming followed the pace boat. Style swim to the surface bounding an interesting attraction.
3.	Sea Turtle	Arakan	Seeing the turtles lay their eggs in the distance is an unforgettable experience.

ecotourism area.

This study aims to evaluate the potential of ecotourism in the Arakan-Wawontulap coastal region, and in particular this study wanted to 1) inventory of the potential for ecotourism, including natural resources, local culture, socio-economy of local communities, infrastructure, institutional, and possible impacts of tourism development in Arakan-Wawontulap coastal region, 2) determine the feasibility of developing a level Arakan-Wawontulap coastal region as an ecotourism area, and 3) design a development strategy Arakan-Wawontulap coastal

region as an ecotourism area.

Methodology

The study was conducted in the Arakan-Wawontulap coastal region. Research carried out for 4 months, from February to May 2010. Data were collected by using questionnaires, interviews, observation, and documentation. Data analysis was carried out in accordance with the purpose of research. Descriptive analysis for the inventory of six aspects of the potential of ecotourism in the area of

the Arakan –Wawontulap coast. Scoring method to determine the feasibility of developing a regional level. SWOT analysis is to find the draft of tourism development strategy.

Results

Inventory of Ecotourism Potential in Arakan-Wawontulap Coastal Region

1. Natural resources - In coastal waters there are some very attractive ecosystems, particularly coral reefs and mangroves (Table 1).

In addition to attractive ecosystem, the coastal waters there are also several attractive biota (Table 2). The presence of biota, these organisms are very closely related to the condition of coastal waters of this region is dominated by mangrove and a broad seagrass areas.

On the mainland coastal ecosystems and biota are also attractive (Table 3). In the area there are 2 forest ecosystem conservation. Forest “Manembo” as a Wildlife region, and Forest “Masewer” as Protection Forest (Anonymous, 2009).

On the mainland coast of the Arakan-Wawontulap also has a variety of sites / hue that is very attractive (Table 4). Site / hue attractive this could be a major supporter of ecosystems and the biota attractive development which have been described previously.

2. Local Culture - Inventory includes aktraksi culture of the local culture, local wisdom, and craft products (Table 5). All forms of local culture this have not yet be developed. Cultural attractions have not been considered as an integral part of everyday life of society. The practice of local wisdom acted by a very limited community. Typical craft is not produced as

Table 3. Ecosystem and Biota Attractive on Mainland Coastal

No.	Attractive Ecosystem/ Biota	Name of Ecosystem/ Biota	Remarks
1.	Forest	Manembo-nembo Masewer	Protected Forest for Wildlife Protected Forest
2.	Wildlife	Anoa dan Rusa	Habitat in the forest, can be observed drinking in the river in the forest.
3.	Bird	Tangkasi Elang tiram, dara-laut jambul, cekakak sungai, burung-madu sriganti Elang-alap dada merah, pekaka buah-buah	Hiding in a tree in the forest. Birds can also be found elsewhere in the territory of Indonesia. Endemic birds of Sulawesi.

Table 4. Attractive Sites in Mainland Coast

No.	Name	Location	Attractive Value
1.	Poopoh Waterfall	Poopoh Village	Very easy to reach (BTNB, 2010).
2.	Masewer Waterfall	Raprap Village	Reach 7 meters tall, but very difficult to reach (4 km from the village), making it suitable for adventure tourism.
3.	BatuTikar Waterfall	Pinasungkulan Village	Water flows on a flat rock, ramps, and wide (BTNB, 2010).
4.	Small Lake	Poopoh Village	To achieve that goal so far down a path of about 2 km from the village Poopoh.
5.	Kalineran	Around plantation in Kumu village	Is complex and there is an old settlement VOC monument, making it suitable for historical tourism.
6.	Batu Lubang	Pinasungkulan Village	Natural cave made of rock, the mouth of the cave is at the beach and along to the mainland.
7.	‘Pelabuhan’	Sondaken Village	Local port, where fish landing vessels owned by the community. Location coast with waves that are quiet, so that could be used as a recreational beach while burning the fish that are purchased directly from the new ship dock at the port.

Table 5. Diversity of Local Culture in Arakan Coastal Area-Wawontulap

No.	Form	Name	Remarks
1.	Culture Attraction 1) Dance	Masamper	Sangihe typical ethnic dances related to the ceremonial expression of thanksgiving to the Creator.
		Maengket	Minahasa ethnic dances typical of traditional ceremonies associated with harvest, thanksgiving new home, opening new agricultural land, and other thanksgiving.
		Kabasaran	Minahasa ethnic dances that depict typical warrior valor Minahasa.
	2) Tradition	Tulude	Ritual of ethnic Sangihe to express gratitude for the inclusion of God as long as a year has passed and ask God's help for years to come.
		Thanksgiving	Tradition gave thanks to God for the harvest and work in a year. Public worship and carrying the harvest to the church, after it held a dinner-drink with relatives and friends. Usually held in June-July, and roads in this region becomes very bad because it filled with people who want to visit relatives or acquaintances.
		Mandi Safar	Bathroom rollicking on the beach during the day. Held in the month of Safar (2nd month in the Hijri calendar).
2.	Local Wisdom	Bulan 15	In this day on the month are allowed to see Dugong close, as close as it can. In addition this day on the month is not allowed.
		Pante Taturuga	A location on the beach which is devoted to turtles lay their eggs. This location should not be disturbed, because it is believed will affect the fishing catch at sea.
		Goso Blanga	Banning clean kitchen utensils on the beach. If caught will be liable to customs and processions removal must be done, in order to avoid large waves that could damage settlements.
3.	Handicrafts	Fish scales	Fish scales is not discarded, but is processed into various forms of craft, such as miniature boats, dolls tarsiers, and so forth.

part of the tourism industry.

3. Socio-Economic Local Communities - Socio-economic aspects of local community Arakan-Wawontulap coastal region which was described consist of education, occupation, and habits of everyday life. The level of public education in the Arakan-Wawontulap coastal region is low. The amount of 8,368 people live in the Arakan-Wawontulap coastal region, most (43.4%) have only the highest education in primary schools. Some had attained secondary school (14.07%), high school educational level (20.88%) and college level (2,15%). There are about 19.5% of the people who have not or do not complete primary school. Communities job in the Arakan -Wawontulap were varies. Most are farmers (59%), and partly as a fisherman (24%). There is also a work as traders, artisans, civil servants and military and police, and private sector workers. However, the majority of people who have two or three different jobs. This condition is closely related to sub-

sistence farm situations and circumstances that are available. In this area there is sea that could be used as farm incomes, so that people work as fishermen. But if the weather is not good to go to sea, then the people turned to farming. The pattern works like this make the most of the heads of households in this region earned more than six hundred thousand rupiah every month. Means that most families in this region are at adequate levels of income and excluding poor households by category Central Bureau of Statistics and World Bank criteria (Anonymous, 2006). The pattern of work is also greatly affect the habits of people living in this region. If sea conditions allow, the majority of people work as fishermen. If sea conditions do not allow to go to sea, then most of whom work as farmers, artisans, and merchants. In the afternoon most of the village looked calm, because almost all of its people to go to sea or working outside the village. Except on Sunday, almost no one goes to sea or out of the village. People who work outside are usually returned to the village

on Sunday. Because it will be seen bustling village on Sunday. Religious activities and community generally done on Sunday. People in this area are very friendly and appreciate visitors. Customers who visited the village will be treated well. These habits are influenced by the mores of local communities that really appreciate outsiders, though distinct identity. This custom has been established since long time ago.

4. Infrastructure - Inventory of regional infrastructure involves two aspects: physical and non physical infrastructure. Physical infrastructure include accessibility, facilities, structuring the region, and the existence of a tourist attraction. Non-physical infrastructure covering security and the public perception of ecotourism. The level of accessibility Arakan-Wawontulap coastal region is very high. This area can be accessed via land and sea, and can be done throughout the year without having thwarted by weather and season. Communication facilities in the region is relatively good. Some people use a mobile phone facility with a relatively good network signal. But there is no telephone network cable coming into the area, so may not find any family who has a home telephone facilities. Accommodation related to tourism in this region are relatively poor. Some of the cottages can be found around the village Wawontulap and Poopoh village, but all of this cottage is privately owned and is earmarked for activities that are privacy. There is no restaurant, or places to shop in this area. Clean water became one of the main problems most of the villages in the area of the Arakan-Wawontulap. No one village that has no electricity, but no one village who build their own electric facilities, all using electricity from State Electricity Company (PLN). But throughout the region not found any street lighting facilities, so the area looks very dark at night, except in the township-township residents. Village laid out in simple, as is appropriate rural atmosphere. However, some villages look less clean and has not been well laid. Village Wawontulap and Poopoh have abrasion problems. Sea water could reach the township residents, or to inundate the main street when there was a tidal wave. Sondaken Village is the only village that is well neat and clean. Main street village and the hall was built very smooth. In front of the houses built a simple fence that looks neat. Planted many trees around the village, so that the village atmosphere was cool. Of so many objects and color of existing potential in Arakan-Wawontulap coastal region, only

four objects that had been already known to the public as a tourist attraction (Table 6). However, only known by locals only. - Arakan-Wawontulap coastal region is relatively safe. All respondents are asked about regional security through the questionnaire stated that regional security is guaranteed. Communities have the awareness to keep order and security of the village. From the police data is also known that Arakan-Wawontulap coastal region is relatively safe. Perception of local communities in the Arakan-Wawontulap coastal region about ecotourism is still very limited. Of the 110 respondents were asked about ecotourism, some 69% said they had heard but not understood about ecotourism. Approximately 19% of respondents even admitted had never heard of ecotourism. Only about 12% of respondents who have a perception of ecotourism, although with the different concept and the different views.

5. Institutional - Inventory includes institutional and institutional aspects of regulation. Inventory results show that in the Arakan-Wawontulap coastal region doesn't has institutions, both formal and informal, which are directly related to tourism, especially ecotourism development. At the local level, there are three organizations that successfully identified, but they are not directly related to tourism or ecotourism, though indirectly making a positive contribution to the development potential of ecotourism. At the regional level, there are 3 very intensive organizations conducting activities in this area. Three organizations were Bunaken National Park (BTNB), Bunaken National Park Management Board (BNPMAB), and the Concerned Citizens Forum Bunaken National Park (FMPTNB). The three organizations are not directly related to tourism or ecotourism, but indirectly was instrumentally in the development of eco-tourism potential in the region. The weakness of the existence of these institutions in the region is the coordination of programs and activities. Many public opinion which states the existence of the organization often cause problems. From the results of the inventory is known that in the Arakan coastal region-Wawontulap no regulation at the local level relating to the development of tourism or ecotourism. However, some community leaders said that some villages are preparing Perdes (Village regulation) which can be categorized as a positive contribution to the development of tourism and ecotourism in the region. The village Government and community in the process of preparing Poopoh Perdes ownership and use of lands owned by the villagers.

Table 6. Tourism Objects in Arakan-Wawontulap Coastal Region

No.	Name	Location	Description
1.	Tanjung Kelapa	between Poopoh and Teling village.	Black sandy beach, about 150 meters from the village ear. In front of the beach there are areas of coral reefs as a diving spot.
2.	Poopoh lake	Poopoh village	Located in nearby forest areas around Poopoh. Small lake. To reach this location must be along the path to the ground about 2 km from the village Poopoh or 5 km from the village of Rap-rap.
3.	Blok 8	Kumu village	White sandy beach, at low tide reef mounds visible on the left and right.
4.	Tambelang	Popareng village	White sandy beach with waves that are very quiet.

Table 7. Regulations at Nasional Level

No.	Regulations	Concerning	Relation to the Development of Ecotourism in Arakan Coastal Area-Wawontulap
1.	UU No.27 Tahun 2007	Management of Coastal and Small Islands	Government must encourage the business community through various activities in the field of Resource Management Coastal and Small Islands efficient and effective manner.
2.	UU No. 9 Tahun 1990	Tourism	One of the tourism development efforts is to find potential new destinations and leading to ecotourism.
3.	PP No. 67 Tahun 1996	Tourism Organisation	Tourism should be conducted with great attention to the survival of communities and natural resources.
4.	PP No. 18 Tahun 1994	Cultivation of Nature Tourism in National Parks, Forest Park and Nature Park	Business tourism in National Parks is possible does not interfere with the existence region of origin. The purpose of tourism does not damage the purpose and function of an area as a conservation area.
5.	Circular Letter of the Minister of Home Affairs to all Governors (SE No.660.1/836.V/Bangda) On 28 April 2000	Regional Ecotourism Development Guidelines	Trying to develop the potential of regional ecotourism development based on the preservation of local culture. The development of ecotourism in the region should consider seriously the preservation of nature, local culture, and welfare of the community.
6.	Decree of the Minister of Culture and Tourism No. 002/ND/MKP/VII / 2002. July 29, 2002	Determination of five areas of priority tourism development in Indonesia.	One is the Northern Territory Sulawesi and East Kalimantan, covering: Bunaken National Park, and Derawan Islands (Derawan, Charitable, Kakaban, Maratua)

In the village Popareng and Pungkol. designed Perdes prohibiting the sale of liquor. At the regional level, there are two regulations which is strongly associated with the development of ecotourism in the region. Decision of the Director General of Forest Protection and Nature Conservation Decree No. 13/IV-KK/2008 of Zoning Bunaken National Park, and South Minahasa Regency Decree No.95 of 2007 on Development of Regions Minapolitan Tatapaan. At the national level, some regulations that strongly support the development of the coastal area of Arakan - Wawontulap as a conservation area (Table 7). These regulations provide a clear restriction and adequate space for the development of ecotourism in a conser-

vation area, including in-Wawontulap Arakan Coast region.

6. Possible Impact - Possible effects can be observed from the impact on natural resources and the impact on the lives of local communities (Ward, 2004; Dahuri *et al.*, 2008). Impact on natural resources can be seen through changes in the ecosystem and / or changes to the biota in these ecosystems (Kennish, 1998; Darsoprajitno, 2002). Ecotourism is a tourism development concept is most appropriate for conservation areas, such as region-Wawontulap Arakan Coast. Principles of ecotourism is to reduce negative impacts on nature and the environment caused by tourism

Table 8. Scoring Result of Ecotourism Potential in Arakan-Wawontulap Coastal Region

Variable	Category (K)	Scoring (S)		
		Low 1 - 2	Moderate 3	High 4 - 5
1. Natural Resources	1. Waters			
	1) Attractive ecosystem			5
	2) Attractive biota			5
	2. Terrestrial			
2. Local Culture	3) Attractive ecosystem			5
	4) Attractive biota			5
	5) Culture attraction	2		
	6) Local wisdom		3	
Scoring Grade (1) and (2)	7) Handicraft		3	
	$(\sum S/7) \quad (28/7) =$			4
3. Socio-economical Local Communities	8) Education	2		
	9) Type of work and occupation			4
	10) Habits			4
4. Infrastructure	1. Physics			
	11) Accessibility			5
	12) Facility	2		
	13) Arrangement of area		3	
	14) Tourism site	2		
	2. Non physics			
5. Institutional	15) Safety and comfortable			4
	16) Perception about ecotourism	2		
	1. Organization			
	17) Local stage			4
	18) Regional stage		3	
6. Impact Probable	2. Regulation			
	19) Local point			4
	20) Regional point		3	
	21) National point			5
6. Impact Probable	1. on Natural resources			
	22) on ecosystem			5
	23) on biota			5
	2. 24) on local communities			5
Scoring Grade (3), (4), (5), and (6)	$(\sum S/17)$	$(62/17) =$		3,65
Scoring Grade for all Category	$(\sum S/24)$	$(90/24) =$		3,75

activities. Ecotourism is also highly appreciate the local life (cultural, social, and economic). Of all the definitions of ecotourism exist, it is known that in addition to give priority to nature conservation and the environment, ecotourism is also developed with the principle of respect for local life, whether social, economic, and local culture. One of the principles of ecotourism development is a form of travel that are responsible for the existence of biota attractive. Biota attractive is classified as endemic, exotic, and endangered. Object tours offered of a tourist industry concept of ecotourism is conservation of biota attractive, not focused solely on these biota. Biota attractive development could be used as an icon of an object

or area of tourism, but the exposure of its existence must consider aspects of the biology and ecology of these biota. Model development like this is characteristic of an ecotourism industry. One of the criteria of ecotourism is not bothersome especially damaging flora and fauna (Anonymous, 2009). Thus, the development of ecotourism in the area of the Arakan Coast-Wawontulap provide extensive opportunities for local people to develop themselves and improve welfare. Own community who organize and enjoy the results of a developed tourism industry.

Area Development Feasibility Level

Feasibility level Arakan-Wawontulap coastal region

to be developed as ecotourism is at moderate levels (Table 8). Arakan-Wawontulap Coastal Region has potential that is still feasible to be developed as ecotourism.

The development of ecotourism based on natural resources and local culture. Arakan-Wawontulap Coastal Region have the potential of natural resources is very high, although the local culture remains to be explored and developed again. If based on only two aspects of this potential, the Arakan-Wawontulap Coastal Region very feasible to be developed as ecotourism.

Potential Arakan

Wawontulap Coastal Region when viewed from four aspects, namely, infrastructure, socio-economic, institutional, and possible impacts, moderate approach is at a high level. Arakan coastal region-Wawontulap still feasible to be developed as ecotourism, but with more attention and develop some aspects of its existence are still low.

Draft Development Strategy

Strategy of Preparatory the Region and Stakeholders First strategy is to socialize on a) Natural Resources. Arakan-Wawontulap Coastal Region has the potential of natural resources is very high to be developed as a tourist area. This potential should be disseminated to all stakeholders, for early on that all stakeholders are aware of and begin to design concept development. b) The concept of ecotourism. Literature review proves that the concept of ecotourism best practice. Ecotourism is the most minimal negative impact on the sustainability of ecosystems, the existence of biota, and the life of local communities. This concept should be communicated to all stakeholders, so that from the beginning to have the same perceptions and attempt to formulate a plan for sustainable tourism development strategy in the Arakan-Wawontulap Coastal Region. c) Regulations. Arakan-Wawontulap Coastal Region a conservation area, so not just used as a tourist destination. However, there are some regulations that provide space and opportunity to develop tourism in a conservation area. This information should be disseminated to all stakeholders, in order to have an understanding and the same concept for the development of the region.

Next, doing institutional strengthening and restructuring of the region. In the midst of local communities, there are several organizations that

contribute positively to the development of ecotourism. This condition gives the signal that local people have the ability to organize themselves and develop their potential, including for the purpose of tourism development. Therefore, small groups or organizations that exist today are in the midst of local communities, must be maintained, even given the institutional strengthening, and directed to develop their own eco-tourism potential in the region. These groups can be developed to become a local community organization that did the planning, management, supervision, and evaluation of ecotourism development in the Arakan-Wawontulap Coastal Region. Thus, the development of ecotourism in the area of the Arakan-Wawontulap Coastal Region community-based fully or independently developed by the community (community-based development). The concept of community-based development is in line with the spirit of promoting ecotourism and the role of local community participation.

Capacity-Building Strategy

The development of ecotourism in the area of the Arakan-Wawontulap Coastal Region must begin by establishing a clear legal umbrella. Ten villages are located in the region should prepare and establish a Village Regulations (Perdes) together, a set of concepts and strategies for developing ecotourism in the region. Perdes also provides for an institution which is responsible for planning, executing, monitoring, and evaluation of tourism development.

Preparation and establishment of the Joint 'Perdes' coupled with bringing the local organization that is integrated, but has the Arakan-Wawontulap coastal region development authority as ecotourism. No need to establish a new organization, but it can be to utilize and develop local organizations that had been already in the midst of society. These local organizations to design, implement, and evaluate the development of ecotourism in the region. At least this is the organization that sets Spatial Regions Ecotourism, Map and Status ODTW in the Regions, as well as tariff and schedule of visits. That make this institutional guarantee continuity of supply of tourism products is legally (legal Guaranty of supply). This also encourages institutional sectors to foster the spirit of ecotourism and the environment in all elements of society. This integrated institutional as well that make up the concept of ecotourism, which is based on carrying capacity region. Local organizations are also given the responsibility to fix the

facility area, is really in line with the concept of ecotourism development.

The potential of local culture should be explored and developed more leverage, to be able to sustain the natural resource potential is very high in this region. Actually, the potential for local culture is still there, just not diekshloprasi and developed to the fullest. It should be noted that the development of local culture as a tourist attraction should pay attention to the principles of ecotourism. Ecotourism principle requires that the local culture as a tourist attraction presented as part of the real life of local communities, not merely as an artificial attraction and was held to entertain tourists.

Education of local communities must also be increased. This strategy is important to strengthen the understanding, perceptions, and actions of all stakeholders, especially local communities, to the concepts of ecotourism. In the formal education, the government pushed for more active role, for example by building more schools, especially junior and senior high schools in the region, and provide adequate facilities for the community in the region have wider opportunities to increase their education. Local organizations to develop a curriculum that bernuasa ecotourism, then push the formal educational institutions (elementary, junior high school) is in the region and around the area, to implement it as part of school lessons. In the path of non-formal education, strengthening communities were given simultaneously by doing trainings that are closely related to the development of ecotourism. For example, do the counseling ecotourism, lodging operator training, training to make souvenirs, training of tour guides, training frontliner, or other training that supports preparation of eco-tourism infrastructure in the region. Education of local communities is an important key to the development of ecotourism in the region. Development strategy which focuses on the management of Community-Driven Development (community-based development), must be preceded and accompanied by an increase in the quality of public education.

Marketing Strategy

The diversity of ecosystems and the existence of organisms that exist in the region, become icons for the development of ecotourism in Arakan-Wawontulap Coastal Region. Accessibility of the region is very high, which the region can be accessed throughout the year regardless of weather or transportation

facility, used as promotional material profitable (adventage image).

Adventage image of high accessibility must be accompanied by strategies to broaden the spectrum of inventory, in order to capture the micro-market opportunities. The diversity of ecosystems and the existence of biota that exist in the region, can be packaged into a variety of tourism products, ranging from passive nature tourism (eg see the dugong, or snorkeling and enjoying the beauty of coral reefs), to highlight the adventure tourism. The potential there is adventure tourism on ecosystems such as sandy beach in Tanjung Kelapa and in the waters of several villages in the region, to try to find a mini exotic biota, or in these Manembo - nembo and Masewer forest ecosystem to observe the behavior Anoa, Deer, Tangkasi, and several endemic birds. Walking through the forest until it reaches a few waterfalls, small lakes on the estate Poopoh, and VOC monument in Kalineran, requires a lot of effort and stamina. If all components of the strategy has been applied, the ecotourism atmosphere is expected to be present in the Arakan-Wawontulap Coast Region. The atmosphere is the atmosphere ecotourism area filled with the spirit and ecotourism activities. This is the final condition that is expected to create in Arakan-Wawontulap Coast Region as an ecotourism area. Ecotourism atmosphere characterized by the presence of two atmosphere, namely -

1) The existence of the local community is greatly appreciated. Society still perform the activity and work respectively. Not leaving the culture, customs, and habits of good living. If the culture, customs, and habits of life of the attractions of interest to wisatawan, then it does not mean made-or are held for the sake of the show tour, but it really comes as part and parcel of socio- economic life of society.

2) The existence of natural resources are managed sustainably. Commodi-fication is a major conservation and management activities, not natural objects. Thus, tourism activities that many are active tourism conditioned, though not abandon passive tourism. Tourism activity is present as an integral part of conservation and management activities. Sale value of tourism lies in the condition of natural resources is sustainable. The more awake condition of sustainability, the higher the sale price as ecotourism.

Conclusion

Arakan-Wawontulap Coast Region has a very high

potential of natural resources, local culture, socio-economic of local communities. The potential still to be improved in infrastructure, and adequate institutional. All of Arakan-Wawontulap Coast Region potential, shows that the development of this area as an ecotourism is at a moderate level. Arakan-Wawontulap Coast Region considered feasible to be developed as ecotourism.

The draft strategy can be recommended for the development of the Arakan-Wawontulap Coast Region as an ecotourism area, including : preparation of regional strategy and the stakeholders, capacity building strategy, and marketing strategy.

Acknowledgement

This research was supported by United Board for Christian Higher Education in Asia (UBCSEA)

References

- Anonymous, 2006. Fourteen (14) Criteria for Determining Family/Domestic Poor. Central Bureau of Statistics, Jakarta.
- Anonymous, 2008. Naturiana: Bunaken National Park Conservation Area. Articles Environmental Education Through Mass Media. Cooperation Sustainable Production WWF Indonesia Foundation and CIDA.
- Anonymous, 2009. Principles and Criteria for Community-Based Ecotourism. Cooperation Directorate of Tourism Products, Directorate General of Tourism Destination Development, Ministry of Culture and Tourism and WWF-Indonesia.
- Arikunto, S. 2006. *Procedure Research*. A Practical Approach. Publisher Rineka PT Cipta, Jakarta.
- Bakosurtanal (Survei and Mapping Coordination Board) Republic of Indonesia, 2010. Map of North Sulawesi Province. Digital Map Service.
- Ceballos-Lascurain, H. 1996. *Tourism, Ecotourism and Protected Areas*. Gland, Switzerland: IUCN.
- Dahuri, R., Rais, J., Ginting, S.P. and Sitepu, M.J. 2008. *Coastal and Ocean Resources Integrated Management*. Publisher PT Pradnya Paramita, Jakarta.
- Damanik, J. and HF Weber, 2006. *Ecotourism Planning. From Theory to Applications*. GMU Center for Tourism Studies & Publisher Andi, Yogyakarta.
- Darsoprajitno, S. 2002. *Ecological Tourism. Object Management Procedure and Attractions*. Publisher Angkasa, Bandung.
- Fauzi, A. 2006. *Economics of Natural Resources and Environment. Theory and Applications*. Publisher PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama, Jakarta.
- From, A. 2004. Abusing Ecotourism; the rethoric of the noble cause, used for commercial ends. Newsweek Budget Travel Inc.
- Hunt, J. 1989. In: *Search of Adventure*. Talbot Adair Press, New York.
- Lasut, M.T., Jensen dan, K.R. and Shivakoti, G. 2008. Analysis of constraints and potentials for wastewater management in the coastal city of Manado, North Sulawesi, Indonesia. *Journal of Environment Management* 88. 1141-1150.
- Kennish, M. J. 1998. *Pollution Impacts on Marine Biotic Communities*. CRC Press LLC.
- Mehta, A. 1999. Field Manual Bunaken National Park. NRM / EPIQ Program. Manado.
- Minister of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia. Circular letter to all Governors Number 660.1/836.V/Bangda. April 2, 2000. Ecotourism Guidelines for Development of Regions.
- Minister of Culture and Tourism Republic of Indonesia. Decree No. 002/ND/MKP/VII/2002. July 29, 2002. About the Establishment of Five Regional Priority Ecotourism Development in Indonesia.
- Priskin, J. 2001. Assessment of natural resources for nature-based tourism: the case of the central coast region of Western Australia. *Tourism Management Journal*. 22 : 634-648.
- Rangkuti, F. 2008. SWOT analysis techniques dissecting business case. *Reorientation of the Strategic Planning Concept for Facing the 21st Century*. Publisher PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama, Jakarta. Secretariat of State. State Gazette of 1990 No. 12. Law No. 9 / 1990. About Tourism.
- Secretary of State. State Gazette of 2007 No. 84. Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 27 Year 2007. on Management of Coastal Areas and Small Islands.
- Secretariat of State. Government Regulation Number 18 of 1994. About the Exploitation of Nature Tourism in National Parks, Forest Park and Nature Park.
- Secretariat of State. Government Regulation Number 67 of 1996. About Tourism Organization.
- TIES (The International Ecotourism Society), 1991. TIES Global Ecotourism Fact Sheet. UNEP Tourism. www.unep.org
- Turak, E. and DeVantier, L. 2003. Reef-building corals of Bunaken National Park, North Sulawesi, Indonesia: Rapid ecological assessment of biodiversity and status. Final Report to the International Ocean Institute Regional Centre for Australia and the Western Pacific. TOTAL Foundation (France), the International Ocean Institute - Regional Centre for Australia & the Western Pacific, Marine Conservation Action Fund (Boston, Massachusetts) and the University of Sam Ratulangi (Manado, North Sulawesi, Indonesia).
- UNEP. 2000. *Impact of Tourism*. UNEP Tourism. www.unep.org
- Wardhana, W.A. 2004. *Impact of Environmental Pollution*. Revised Edition. Publisher Andi, Yogyakarta.